

TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND OR FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: All living things have some method of communicating with members of their own species; communication is, in the end necessary to their existence. Others make physical movements or facial expressions, while others use vocal noises. Many individuals use a range of techniques. Animals use loud sounds and facial expressions like showing teeth, whereas birds primarily use vocal signals in addition to body movements to convey their intentions. Insects use body movements, with bees' many "dances" being the most well-known.

Keywords: learning a second language, general English proficiency, a first language, a foreign language, ELF, teaching and learning, a multicultural, multiethnic, multilingual nation Different linguistic, cultural, and religious origins, primary and high schools, the "teacher-student" system, Language Center English lessons, English courses.

INTRODUCTION

The pupils are from a variety of backgrounds. Within this context, the Language Center university, which ranges from general English abilities up to academic and ESP, provides English classes to all students from all faculties.

The teaching and study of English in this setting is very difficult for both parties given the mix of teachers and pupils . The biggest challenge in teaching a foreign language—in this example, English—is the teacher's uncertainty about whether to utilize the student's native tongue or not. This essay focuses on the issue of whether the L1 is used in ELF instruction at SEEU's English Language Center programs. If so, how frequently and when is it employed? In order to meet the demands of students who

have been raised and educated in a multilingual environment, the methodological tactics English teachers use are examined and elaborated in this study. Both quantitative and qualitative methodologies were used to analyze the data that were gathered for this article. The results of this study indicate that balanced and cautious L1 usage in English lessons does not appear to have an impact on students' exposure to the target language. The classes are assigned to pupils in elementary and high school. When teaching a foreign language, in particular, this variety in the classroom can often make it difficult to use the L1.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Multilingualism is "a condition in which more than two languages are used in the same setting for similar purposes," according to Poudel, P. P. (2010:121). Teaching in such a varied environment raises concerns since the teacher must oversee a class of pupils who come from various linguistic, cultural, and religious backgrounds. In many situations, employing students' L1 might actually waste the time intended for teaching and learning. If the instructor is not fluent in all of the pupils' native languages, there is still another issue to consider. In contrast, if L1 is utilized, teachers must ensure that all pupils have an equal chance to succeed in order to avoid discriminating against anybody.

Instructors are educated to show and explain vocabulary or any other language issue using synonyms, antonyms, gestures, or mime. By employing these tactics, instructors may be able to avoid speaking L1 in the classroom. Although it is against Language Center policy to use any other language than English for instruction, both teachers and students are tempted to do so when taking English classes. In this essay, I'll talk about how the L1 is used in English lessons and how it helps students learn the target language.

Review of the literature The mother tongue plays a positive impact in the learning and acquisition of a second language, according to EFL teachers who base this argument on their own experiences learning a foreign language.

The learning of EFL is greatly impacted by the use of L1. According to a lot of academics, people who are learning a second language do so by applying what they already know about their first language. They can deal with encounters and communication issues by putting this method into practice. Studies have revealed that when learning a second language, individuals draw on their past knowledge of their original tongue and background experiences. While attempting to read, speak, or write in the second language, they use structures from their first language that are similar to the second language to transfer forms and meanings. The use of L1 in EFL lessons has long been a contentious issue. Scholars have divided into two factions in response to this question. On the one hand, there are those who advocate for the use of L1, like Atkinson (1987), who fervently believes that students' mother tongues shouldn't be totally disregarded in English classes because "the use of L1 can be very effective in terms of the amount of time spent explaining" (Atkinson, 1987:242). On the other hand, some people are opposed to using L1, arguing that doing so limits pupils' exposure to the target language.

There seems to be a growing belief among some second language acquisition teachers that the first language (L1) facilitates the learning of the second language (Schweer, 1999). Additionally, according to Ferrer (2000), a significant number of teachers who were inspired by their own experiences as second language learners assert that the mother tongue plays an active and advantageous role in second language instruction. In his statement that "the L1-L2 connection is an undeniable fact of life, whether we like it or not the new knowledge is learned on the basis of the previously acquired language," Stern (1992) suggests that L1 and L2 cannot be considered separately.

ANALYSIS

According to his study, it will be beneficial to prevent the target language's understanding if L1 is not used. According to the author's further explanation, learning a language will not be successful if the learner lacks understanding. For this reason, the

author encourages the use of L1 when it is deemed essential. Macaro (2005:532) notes that avoiding the L1 increases the use of input modification, which is time-consuming and dulls and lessens the realism of the instruction. Examples of input modification include repetition, speaking more slowly, switching out simple words for more complicated ones, simplifying grammar, etc. According to Nunan and Lamb (1996), L1 is unavoidable during the learning process, especially at low levels, in light of these factors.

Techniques for Teaching English, As a result of the Tower of Babel's builders speaking many languages, society started to require interpreters.

Everywhere, interpreters were valued. Prior to recently, learning a foreign language was more of a pastime than a harsh reality. Knowing a foreign language implied being an esthete, a member of an exclusive group, or (the least sinister possibility) an oddball. However, times are altering.

As you are aware, every house starts with an architectural plan. We are now becoming less and less afraid of the enormous fortification known as "Foreign Language," on top of which a flag—often the British one—flies triumphantly. And in this instance, understanding contemporary instructional techniques will act as the crucial plan. The question "What method do you use to teach?" has recently become more and more pertinent as the market for educational technology is flooded with ideas for a wide range of English learning methods, which suggests a rise in the culture of intellectual product consumption.

Increasingly, a bewildered applicant, student, or businessman (but also a student) stops in front of bookcases filled with language literature and media aids or thoughtfully scans a lengthy list. The price is a deciding factor, but the most important ones are "English in two weeks" and "Communicative

Eventually, you'll learn about "English teaching methods", "English with Englishmen in Moscow", "Effective express method", and "English at the subconscious level". There is so much new and unexplored! And this raises questions

about the outcomes. Do you have faith in current technology? Or like well-known "brands" like "Bonk," "Eckersley," or "Headway," which are edging closer to being regarded as methodological classics? At the turn of the century, the fact still stands. The techniques of teaching English underwent a "revolution" in Russia. Grammar, nearly mechanical vocabulary knowledge, reading, and literary translation were formerly all given top priority without a second thought.

These are the tenets of the "old school," which, to be fair, nonetheless produced results, but at what cost? Long hours of repetitive work were required to learn a language. The exercises on the material, as well as the reading, translating, memorization of new terms, and recounting of the assignments, were all rather repetitive. An essay or dictation may be given sometimes, along with phonetic exercises as a break, to provide the essential activity change. Only one function of the brain was used when reading and working on "topics" Not at all . It was unexpected that so few people were fluent in the language: only extremely focused and It might be high level mastered by diligent individuals. However, they could easily compete with Cambridge graduates in terms of grammar ability! True, they were well compensated for their labor because in our nation, being a translator or a foreign language teacher was a very prestigious job.

DISCUSSION

Now, in order to maintain this high social status, a lot of diligence, perseverance, and daily work are needed. What is actually "revolutionary" is that the majority of people can now access language in some way. And the offer is becoming increasingly customer-focused. Why, for instance, would the secretary willfully learn unneeded information regarding the palatalization . A manager or secretary-assistant who is focused on the 8-hour workday, or as it is commonly referred to, "monopoly" office work development of extremely specialized knowledge and abilities, or on the use of a particular market group for educational programs for learning English. S.G. Ter-Minasova, a renowned expert in linguistics and foreign language teaching techniques,

correctly observes that language acquisition has lately performed better: "The enormous demand needed an unprecedented supply.

Unexpectedly, foreign language instructors became the center of attention for the general public. Thousands of eager experts in several sectors of science, culture, industry, technology, and all other facets of human activity requested that foreign languages be taught right now as a means of production. They have little interest in the philosophy or history of the language and only use foreign languages, particularly English, for utilitarian purposes in order to communicate effectively with individuals from other nations in a variety of social contexts. Going to work, having one-on-one lessons with a teacher, visiting a student at home, "weekend" groups, for both busy and less busy people, and for "pioneers" have all made life substantially easier. who are the material's creator, the location in which it was created, and the people involved tested?

While it used to be comparatively abstract and theoretical, language teaching now has an applied aspect. Even Aristotle introduced the well-known "triad of ethics" in teaching, which completely satisfies contemporary standards: logos, which refers to the caliber of presentation, pathos, which refers to audience interaction, and ethos, which refers to the attitude toward other people. The speaker, the actor, and the foreign language instructor—whose job likewise takes the first two hypostases—all fall under the umbrella of this rule. The roles that teachers play in the educational process have undergone tremendous transformation.

A teacher-mentor or teacher-dictator cannot provide pupils the freedom of choice and the "freedom of learning" required for the understanding of something as nuanced as language. As a result, this unfavorable educational image is gradually becoming a part of history. He was replaced by a leader, a mediator, an observation teacher, and a "pacifier" teacher. While the teacher's personality in this instance recedes into the background, its impact on the audience, which in turn becomes more intimate, does not lessen, but instead increases. In contrast, group contact (between 10 and 15 students) is often organized by the teacher in current Russian and international courses. The basic

approach to this is highly regarded in linguistic universities. The translator is never certain of his familiarity with .

He is fluent in a second language and is aware of the unpredictable nature of new communication circumstances. When studying using the classical method, students learn to not only work with a wide range of lexical layers but also to view the world as a "native speaker"—a native speaker.

N.A. Bonk is arguably the most well-known practitioner of the traditional approach of teaching a foreign language. Her co-authored English textbooks have endured the current competition and have long since established themselves as classics in the field. No one guarantees that using the classical methodology, also known as the fundamental method, will be simple or straightforward for you.

The basic technique presupposes that you enjoy asking "why?"

That you are prepared to enter a fascinating, complicated, and incredibly logical universe known as the linguistic system, and that you will not be satisfied with the justifications "it should be so."

CONCLUSION

The traditional strategy for learning a foreign language. The traditional technique to learning a foreign language has undergone certain changes in this respect, but the unchanging fundamentals of the "classics" of learning the Russian language have been kept. They are occasionally actively employed in schools following alternative methodological trajectories. The traditional course is designed for pupils of all ages and typically entails learning the language "from scratch." The conventional but crucial duties of the instructor include the development of pronunciation, the creation of a grammatical foundation, and the removal of linguistic and psychological barriers to communication. "Classics" did not alter the objectives, but the new strategy has already changed the techniques.

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